

Why Do Dirac Particles and Photons Have Different Spin?

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We have argued in a previous note that a quantum particle has an inherent time interval given by \hbar/E and an inherent ruler length given by \hbar/p . We then argued that spin should be an inherent property which defines 3-space because p only defines one direction in space. Given that a photon and particle with rest mass both follow \hbar/p and \hbar/E , why is their spin different?

We first note that in order 3-space one needs three orthogonal axes. If one were to have $A \times B = \text{momentum density}$, then A and B lie in a plane perpendicular to p density and are not parallel. In other words a set of 3-space axes is present. If one tries to apply this picture to a photon, then one might consider scalar energy density as following from $A \cdot A + B \cdot B$. If A and B are perpendicular, there is no need to consider $A \cdot B$. Given that a photon has no rest frame, one may consider a continuity equation: $d/dt \text{ partial } (A \cdot A + B \cdot B) + \text{grad partial dot } A \times B = 0$.

One may ask whether such an equation may apply to a particle with rest mass. One may note that for momentum in the x direction, the continuity equation is of the form: $d/dt \text{ partial } f(x,t) + d/dx g(x,t) = 0$. This suggests a solution with $f=g = h(ax+bt)$. In other words, x and t always have a weight. In the case of a rest frame, there is a clock, but no need for an x position and so it is unusual that there would be weights for x and t in all frames. We, however, try to consider another argument. For a rest frame, one has energy m_0 and so momentum must be proportional to mv . We try to find A and B values which are consistent with $m_0/\sqrt{1-v^2}$ ($c=1$) and $p=mv/\sqrt{1-v^2}$. This becomes a problem. Next, the $d/dt \text{ partial}$ and d/dx features lead to problems when one considers the rest frame. Thus, the continuity equation, which may be linearized to yield e_{ijk} (Levi Civita) as a spin matrix does not seem to apply to a particle with rest mass, suggesting that such a particle has a different spin (namely $.5$ given by Dirac's theory which is not considered here).

Three-Space Defined by a Quantum Particle

Both a photon and particle with rest mass have free energy and momentum and a quantum frequency of \hbar/E and ruler length of \hbar/p . They do, however, have different dispersion relations: $E^2 = p^2 + m_0^2$ ($c=1$) and $E=pc$.

We have argued in previous notes that a clock interval and ruler length are carried by a quantum particle, but suggested that spin should carry the sense of 3-space because momentum only represents one direction.

If this is the case, it seems that the simplest way to create a 3-axis is to have:

$$A \times B = \text{momentum density} \quad ((1))$$

In such a case, A and B are perpendicular to momentum and may be perpendicular to each other. Then one may define energy density as: $A \cdot A + B \cdot B$ ((2)).

Finally, one may suggest a continuity equation:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } (\text{A dot A} \pm \text{B dot B}) + \text{grad partial dot } (\text{A} \times \text{B}) = 0 \quad ((3))$$

If one considers momentum in the x direction, then:

$$d/dt \text{ partial } f(x,t) + d/dx g(x,t) = 0 \quad ((4)) \quad \text{A solution is } f=g= h(ax+bt)$$

$$\text{such that: } b+a=0 \quad ((5))$$

This suggests weights for x and t in any frame which is fine for a photon because it is always moving. A particle with rest mass, however, does not need an x position in the rest frame and so it is not clear why there should be an ax+bt argument.

We, however, try to consider the particle in a rest frame in more detail. We first note that because there is an m_0 (rest mass) in the rest frame, when given a velocity, one would expect a flux proportional to mv . In fact, from special relativity, one has:

$$E = m_0 / \sqrt{1-vv} \quad \text{and} \quad p = mv / \sqrt{1-vv} \quad (c=1) \quad ((6))$$

Given that energy is m_0 in the rest frame, we ask whether one may find a compatible A and B.

$$\text{If one chooses: } A = \sqrt{m_0} / (1-vv)^{.75} \quad \text{and} \quad B = \sqrt{m_0} v / (1-vv)^{.75} \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Then: } AA - BB = m_0 / \sqrt{1-vv}, \quad \text{but} \quad Ax B = AB = m_0 v / \{ (1-vv) \sqrt{1-vv} \} \quad ((8))$$

Thus, it seems that there are problems finding a compatible A and B. Further problems arise if one tries to introduce time-space dependence. If one only adds $f(x,t)$ to B, then $B \text{ dot } B = BB$ has $f(x,t)f(x,t)$ while $Ax B = AB$ has $f(x,t)$ dependence. For a real function which is periodic this seems to be a problem. Thus, one must suggest both A and B having space-time functions, but this means that in the rest frame A still has a x-t dependence when it should only have t dependence. Thus, for several reasons, it seems one cannot use the $Ax B = \text{momentum}$ approach for a particle with rest mass, even though it seems to apply for a photon.

To obtain spin for a photon, one may linearize the continuity equation and find the term:

$$E_{ijk} d_j \text{ partial } (A + B k) \quad ((9))$$

Thus, e_{ijk} , the Levi-Civita symbol becomes the spin matrix and it is 3x3.

What Does One Do For a Particle with Rest Mass?

A different approach is required for a particle with rest mass. This follows from:

$$E^2 = p^2 + m^2 \text{ versus } E=pc \quad ((10))$$

For $E=pc$ no matrix is required in a frame with p along the x axis, but for $E=i\hbar\partial/\partial t$ and $p=-i\hbar\partial/\partial x$, even with p in the x direction, one requires matrix p when linearizing $E^2=p^2+m^2$ as Dirac has shown. As a result, one finds a 2×2 Pauli matrix governing spin in the particle with rest mass case. Given that this suggests spin up or down, one has two extra degrees of freedom in addition to the direction of p .

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a photon and particle with rest mass do not have the same spin. We suggest that a quantum object should carry spin in order to define 3-space, with momentum lying along one direction. The simplest way to accomplish this is to have $\mathbf{A} \times \mathbf{B} = \text{momentum density}$ with \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} being perpendicular and in a plane perpendicular to momentum. One may then suggest that $E = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{A} \pm \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B}$ and establish a continuity with $\partial/\partial t$ acting on energy density and $\text{grad} \cdot \partial$ acting on momentum density. This seems to apply for a photon which is always moving. If, however, one considers a particle with rest mass, we try to show that such an equation does not hold. Thus, linearizing the continuity equation for a photon leads to a term: $\epsilon_{ijk} \partial/\partial x_j (A+B)_k$ with ϵ_{ijk} , the Levi-Civita symbol, being the spin matrix. For a particle with rest mass, one must linearize $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ using Dirac's approach to find a 2×2 Pauli matrix and spin $1/2$.